

Methods of Activation for Large Groups in Applied University Teaching

Activating methods suitable for large groups generally differ from those for smaller groups in that they are less time-consuming to conduct and usually do not involve presenting all group work results.

For all types of activating methods, i.e., including the following, you must give clear work assignments and should communicate the exact time of completion along with the specific time when the task should be completed. For more complex tasks, it is useful to write down the work instruction for all to see, e.g. on a PowerPoint slide.

Specific activation methods for large groups are presented below:

- Show similarities
- Solution by raising a hand
- Number-Estimation Question
- Call-out Question
- Headstand method
- Buzz Group
- One-Minute-Paper
- Determine order
- Solution in the row of seats

Show similarities

Ask the group several questions that allow you to get an initial overview of the group composition. Those to whom the asked aspect applies in each case should signal this to you by raising their hand. This will give you, for example, information on the prior knowledge of the students in larger groups.

Sample questions:

- Who is a student of a technical subject? Who is a student of economics ... Social sciences... Computer science?
- Who has already attended a session on this topic? Who has already gained practical experience in this field? Who already knows the theory ...?

The students are easily activated by raising their hands and, as a positive side effect, recognize possible commonalities with others. They can then exchange ideas about this after the session.

Digital version

You use a polling tool like Tweedback or PINGO to solicit responses (some video platforms have polling capabilities built in as well). Show the results live on your screen, which you've shared in advance. You can also use hand raising for yes/no questions.

Solution by raising a hand

Set a task and present a range of possible solutions, only one of which is correct, for example: *"Who got result x in this task? Who got result y? ..."*.

All participants are asked to indicate which answer they think is correct by raising their hand. Then explain the correct solution. Alternatively, students can indicate their answer by lifting up their writing block. For example, a block held up vertically represents answer choice a), holding it horizontally signals answer b), and holding it at an angle signals a possible answer c). This often has an interesting effect. If students are unsure of their answer, they hold the writing block partly in front of their face in order to remain "anonymous" in case of a wrong answer.

Digital version

Use a polling tool as in the previously presented method of "Show similarities". In this method, questions should be asked that relate to the students' understanding of a particular issue.

Number-Estimation Question

Consider a number-estimation question, with the task for students to estimate the specific value, if possible. For example, a possible number-estimation question from the medical field is, *"What do you think: What percentage of medications purchased by patients are actually taken by them?"*

Your participants are now given the task of thinking about the question and writing down their answer in large print on a sheet of paper that you can see, preferably with a thick pen. When prompted, everyone holds up their solutions. Get an overview of the values noted and summarize the range of results that occur, without pointing to the students with extreme estimates, which might make them uncomfortable. In addition, you can ask if someone would like to briefly justify their estimate.

In the case of interesting estimation questions, the students' attention rises sharply, as they are very interested in finding out how close their value is to the correct solution. This method is especially good for rebuilding tension when the general concentration of the group wanes.

Digital version

You ask the students to write their answer in the chat. Use the waterfall method, i.e. the students only send their answers at the same time as your signal. Alternatively, have students write down the estimates anonymously on an Etherpad. Read out some of the estimates before revealing the official solution.

Call-out Question

The call-out question, a facilitation technique, is a very easy method to collect input from participants. Write down a question on the board or a flipchart as a heading. After a short period of reflection, the students should call out their answers to you, without asking for them. You write down all the ideas on the medium for all to see, preferably exactly as they were formulated. If necessary, you can ask how to write down the contribution in summary. Do not evaluate or comment on the ideas and do not allow discussions to arise during the collection phase. If a seemingly joking word contribution comes in, ask if you should write it down verbatim. In most cases, the person in question will then tell you that it was just a joke. The goal of this method is to quickly gather ideas. It also gives you an overview of what knowledge your students already have on the subject.

Digital version

Use a digital whiteboard on which you position the question centrally. You can allow students to post terms directly on the board. Alternatively, you can allow "calling out" via microphone or via chat. Then you can also write down the terms on a simple presentation slide. Another option is an Etherpad, where you post the question and all students can write down their terms anonymously under the question (there is a risk here that posts will also be deleted).

Headstand method

You use an inverse question for your questions. For example, if you want to compile "Criteria for good presentations" as the goal of the exercise, ask how to design a presentation so that it is confusing, uninteresting, and incomprehensible. Collect these criteria, for example, using a knowledge pool. Afterwards, ask the students to develop the opposite based on this compilation.

The headstand method can be meaningfully used when it is a matter of waking up the auditorium again, or being able to think creatively again as casually as possible when the thought structure is stuck. With inverse questioning, students often have a very good time, and there is a lot of laughter. During and after the processing of the task, everyone is then awake again.

Digital version

You use the "Calls for comment" method presented above.

Buzz Group

The buzz group has several variations and is a method that has a high acceptance among students and lecturers. The lecturer asks a question to the group that is not too complex or gives a simple discussion assignment. The complementary action statement is: "As you sit, please form a group with the person (or two people) immediately next to you and discuss what I just presented for two minutes."

After two, or if you have given more time, after a maximum of five minutes, ask for silence. In courses with up to a maximum of 15 students, it is possible for you to ask for all the results of the discussion directly; for larger groups, have them provide you with a few exemplary results. This will give you immediate feedback on whether the small groups were able to complete the tasks successfully. As always, if the students actively contribute with their ideas, you show your appreciation on the one hand and encourage their motivation on the other hand when they have little feelings of success: "I have actively contributed!"

Digital version

Set up break-out rooms with a few students for about 3 minutes. Then ask some of the groups to report the answer they found to the question.

One-Minute-Paper

This method allows you to collect feedback in a time-efficient way. You collect the written feedback and, if time permits, present the most important results in summary form at the next session.

Ask the participants to write down on a sheet of paper handed out by you, on which up to three questions are noted or on a DIN-A5 or DIN-A6 sheet of paper of their own, what they particularly liked about the session and, in addition, what they would like to have changed in the next sessions. Point out that only one concise answer should be formulated at a time.

Here are some suggestions for questions:

- What was the main point of the session for you today?
- What is the main question that remained unanswered for you today?
- What is the most important insight for you to take away from this session?
- Which argument did not convince you?

For example, with the first question, you direct students to the overall context of the previous unit. The second question gives you immediate feedback on where they had difficulties in understanding. You then evaluate the results for yourself. In the following session, you can present the results and also discuss them with the students. Be careful not to have to justify yourself when you respond to the students'

criticisms or suggestions for improvement. Even if the evaluation of larger groups involves a relatively large amount of work, it is worth using this method, as experience has shown that you will receive more concrete answers than is often the case with standard evaluation forms.

Digital version

The same task can be used with the help of a learning platform via the feedback function.

Determine order

The basic elements of a process are written unsorted on the board or written down on cards and stuck to the board with scotch tape. Students are given the task of determining the correct order of the terms. They are asked to call out the first term of the process. If different suggestions come up, briefly discuss which one is probably correct with the whole group. The correct term is written down first or the card with the correct term is put up on the board. Then the group should name the second term and so on.

Example of an "order question": In what order do groups commonly go through the following phases of group dynamics according to Tuckman's model: Storming, Forming, Performing, Adjourning, Norming?

Correct order: Forming, Storming, Norming, Performing and Adjourning.

Digital version

Use a digital whiteboard on which you have set the terms as cards. Have students post their own cards with these terms and put them in order. Comment on the process. Alternatively, write down on a presentation slide all of the terms in the process in five different orders, one being the correct order. Using a digital voting tool, the students should now decide which order they think is correct.

Solution in the row of seats

In all rows of seats, the person sitting furthest to the left is handed a worksheet on which a task is noted that is to be solved using the content previously worked on in the session. All rows receive the same worksheet.

Example question, "What ten technical terms do you remember from this course?"

After the start signal, the sheet is passed from left to right in all rows. Everyone in the row who knows an answer writes it on the sheet. The person sitting on the far right of the row must check whether the task has been completely fulfilled. If this is not the case, the missing answers must be filled in in the row of seats. The group whose sheet is the first to arrive completely filled in correctly on the right in their row reports. The fastest group presents its result and wins if the task has been completely solved.

To encourage motivation, which is usually not necessary in a series game, a reward can be offered to the winning group: The "winning row" can, for example, receive a box of small chocolate bars or small bags of jelly beans.

Digital version

They use breakout rooms to virtually map the rows of chairs. Each group receives a task as described above and gets its own etherpad to document its result. For example, once a group has found the number of terms to be achieved, the group leaves the breakout room. Give the other groups a little more time and then bring all the groups back into the main room where the "winning group" gets to present their result.

Wendorff, J. (2021): *Aktivierung von Großgruppen*, in: Waldherr, F./ Walter, C.: *Didaktisch und praktisch - Methoden und Medien für die Präsenz- und Onlinelehre*. 3. überarbeitete und erweiterte Auflage, Stuttgart: Schäffer- Poeschel. P. 81-90